

DETERMINANTS OF CONSUMERS' BUYING BEHAVIOUR WITH REFERENCE TO THE ECO-FRIENDLY FOOD PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

Abstract: Buying eco-friendly food products plays a vital role in promoting sustainable development, environmental protection, and human well-being. One of the major significances is environmental conservation. Eco-friendly food products are produced using natural farming methods that minimize the use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides, thereby reducing soil degradation, water pollution, and biodiversity loss. The main objective of this research is to study determinants of buying behaviour with reference to the eco-friendly food products in Kolar District. The respondents who uses eco-friendly products are the main target audience to collect the data. There were 892 respondents were targeted to collect the data. Convenient sampling techniques were used for the study purpose. and a structured questionnaire was used for the field survey as a data collection tool. Linear regression analysis was used to analyze the data. The research revealed that both buyer's perspective and market conditions are the variables significantly influencing purchasing of Eco-friendly food products by the consumers of Kolar district.

Keywords: Eco-friendly, Food, Products, Buyer, Behavior, Kolar,

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1.INTRODUCTION

The use of food items "that respond to basic needs and bring a better quality of life, while minimizing the use of natural resources, toxic materials, and emissions of waste and pollutants over the life cycle, so as not to jeopardize the needs of future generations" is referred to as consumption. Li, L., and Yang, S. (2018). Customers are crucial to food consumption, and their actions stress the ecosystem in two ways. U. Schrader (2011). The fact that many customers voice concerns about the environment yet do not always take action is scarcely unexpected. T. Jackson (2014). In other words, there is a significant difference between the buyer's mindset and the actual purchase of sustainable food goods, or the attitude-behavior gap, despite the fact that consumer attitudes toward environmental sustainability are generally positive. New consuming habits that are more focused on social, economic, and environmental sustainability have been sparked in recent years by consumers' growing

concerns about food safety, environmental sustainability, and social justice issues. Bostan, I., and Roman, T. (2015). This involves the expansion of alternative distribution chains that highlight the significance of local food production, as well as the rising consumer desire for sustainable food, local food, and other sustainable food and beverage consumption. In order to comprehend and influence ESFC, a goal-directed framework is first constructed. The framework's central premise is that, similar to most human activity, eating is either purposefully or inadvertently motivated by achieving objectives (Xiao, J.J.; Li, H. 2010). Food corporations' marketing campaigns have also influenced dietary standards, population-level preferences for food and drink categories, and the customs, traditions, and values that support eating habits. Liu, Y.; Qu, Y.; Lei, Z. (2017). Human societies place a great deal of importance on food choices and behaviors, and food intake extends well beyond its practical use as a means of survival. Since eating habits have a major role on people's lifestyles and sociocultural surroundings, they are infamously difficult to alter. From a goal-directed viewpoint, food consumption can be focused on reducing negative environmental effects, but individuals also purchase and consume food items to satiate their hunger, experience sensory pleasure, communicate their social standing, adhere to conventions and reference groups, etc. Accordingly, vegetarians and vegans consider the environment as just another justification for sticking to a meatless diet, among other reasons, according to their review, which sought to understand consumers' views towards reducing meat consumption. They also discovered that attitudes on meat, diet, and individual conduct hinder consumer knowledge. The authors specifically discovered that consumers who are health-conscious had an impact on the category of ready-to-eat items, particularly fresh-cut fruits. ESFC is exemplified by eating more plant-based or insect-based meals, consuming less meat, and choosing seasonal goods. Purchasing food that is produced locally and/or sustainably may also be more ecologically friendly in some but not all situations. Although many people already have favorable opinions about sustainable food, there is still a significant gap between the buyer's mindset and the actual purchase and consumption of more sustainable food products. M. Phipps (2012). Customers' propensity to purchase a food product was discovered to be influenced by factors such as flavor, nutrition, and health (Paavola, J. 2001). This demonstrated how hedonistic and altruistic motivations—the latter reinforced by a sense of self-responsibility connected to the preservation of society and the environment—overlap to produce the trend towards sustainable consumption patterns. The shift towards sustainable consumption behaviors in India appears to be motivated by ethical considerations as well (Abdulrazak, S. 2017). The current study attempts to contribute to behavioral solutions for environmental concerns in the food domain by developing a thorough theoretical framework in which we incorporate scholarly ideas and research findings from several disciplines (Sharma, R.; Jha, M. 2017). In relation to sustainable consumption, which is one of the primary production examples of sustainable consumption practices, (Kadic-Maglajlic, S. 2019) highlighted that consumers' growing interest in sustainable food products is not only a result of their desire to preserve rural areas or protect the environment, but it has also been demonstrated that consumer preferences for sustainable extra-virgin olive oil are primarily driven by the perceived benefits of sustainable food consumption on health issues. Additionally, (Epstein, M.J. 2014) has emphasized the preference for health attributes. Furthermore, Quoquab, F. and Mohammad, J. (2019) demonstrated that the consumer's convenience orientation was a factor in the trend toward the choice

for the health characteristic and that it was not just associated with green goods. Due to their complexity, food-related decisions can be influenced by a variety of social, cognitive, emotional, and environmental factors. In conclusion, initiatives to support ESFC compete with other contextual factors that affect people's dietary decisions. Adopting sustainable consumption behaviors is necessary due to the increasing threat to the environment. Knowing the end user is essential to comprehending and creating the best plan for sustainable consumption. This is due to the fact that buyer choice, consumer awareness, choices, behaviors, and lifestyles all influence the strategy to be used in order to accomplish sustainable development, which is one of the most important agreements to emerge in the past ten years. Pretner, G.; Testa, F. (2020). Customers' interest in a Buyers Diet consciousness is driven by the perception that these products promote good health while also being environmentally friendly, according to Tanner (2003), who emphasized the significance of a product's health attribute as an important driver of sustainable consumption practices among consumers. Additionally, as seen by the increasing number of vegan customers in their sample, they emphasized in their study that the trend towards a plant-based diet is also maintained for ethical grounds (Robert, K.W. 2005).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Diverse demographic groups differ in their perspectives on and readiness to embrace sustainable eating practices. Although society may accept sustainable consumption in theory, this does not always result in sustainable consumption behavior, which is more likely to be associated with awareness of the long-term consequences over the natural or social environment, being controlled consumption for the sake of the environment (Vecchio, R.; Annunziata, A. 2013). According to (Dolnicar, S.; Grün, B. 2008), there are purchase obstacles since the market share of sustainable food is lower than the stated desires. Global eating habits are unsustainable (Zahra, S.; McCarthy, B. 2021). (Tung, T.-Y.; Koenig, H.F.2017) used a self-report scale to assess three aspects of the low effect of sustainable consumption behavior: the quality of life, the preservation of the environment, and the resources for future generations (Agentia de 2021). Customers are keen to adopt sustainability, yet obstacles still exist. It highlights how crucial policy action is to promoting behavior change (Autio, M.; Heininen, V. 2004). In high-income nations, where overconsumption of animal proteins (especially red meat), discretionary foods, and ultra-processed foods (UPFs) is common, a decrease in reliance on animal-based foods, particularly ruminant meat, and an increase in reliance on whole plant-based foods will continue to be crucial, even though the composition of such diets will vary depending on the country context. In addition to the aforementioned factors, consumers' sentiments of pride, remorse, respect, and fury also have an impact on their sustainable purchase selections. While consumer guilt has both direct and indirect effects on the desire to buy green items, customer effectiveness as perceived by the consumer is the most potent factor on green purchase intention. It is crucial to look for alternatives and adopt sustainable consumption practices as climate change continues to wreak devastation on ecosystems. In order to maintain a positive reputation in the marketplace, businesses recognized the significance of sustainable development and consumption and incorporated it into their present strategies. Strictly speaking, in order to design appropriate private strategies and governmental policies intended to lessen the detrimental effects on sustainable development, it is required to examine consumer behavior in

relation to sustainable consumption. Factors Influencing Sustainable Consumer Behavior Several academics have examined sustainable consumption and the consumer's involvement. According to (Resurreccion, 2015), customers may be divided into three groups based on how they perceive sustainable food: (i) Responsible food consumers, who make up the largest group, are mature consumers between the ages of 29 and 35 who pay close attention to what they eat, care about the environment, and prefer local food; (ii) inattentive food consumers are younger students from rural areas who have medium incomes and are uninterested in food or the environment; and (iii) potentially sustainable food consumers are people who find it challenging to find and buy sustainable food despite expressing concerns about environmental issues. Flavor, affordability, health, and environmental sustainability are the most often mentioned factors when choosing food, and people are eager to embrace sustainability for the sake of the environment. Young customers' intentions to purchase green products are known to be mostly influenced by their views and environmental concerns. It has been demonstrated that young Indian customers are conscious of current environmental challenges and have a positive attitude toward buying eco-friendly products for future use (Osikomina, J.; Bocken, 2020). Green consumerism is thought to have a lot of potential among people. In Pakistan, the focus on sustainable consumption resulted in the development of a meat consumption scale. Many studies have been done on this topic (Han, Y.; Hansen, H. 2012), and the term "sustainability" has been found to be a broad phrase that has been categorized on a number of levels, from zero food waste to sustainable food to renewable packaging. The concept of sustainability is complex and requires a flexible, balanced, and context-sensitive approach. Customers see sustainability as an essential component of their lifestyle, especially when it comes to consumption, rather than as a concept confined to the manufacturing stage. (Brumă, I.S.; Ulman, S.-R., 2021). Other researchers have also examined the attitude-behavior gap in relation to many forms of sustainable consumption (food, tourism, energy, etc.). Incentives and single labels are one way to bridge the gap in the consumption sector. (Sesini, G.; Castiglioni, C. 2020) noted that academics closely examined green consumerism from the perspective of the relationship between environmental attitudes and behaviors and classified the factors influencing the environment into four categories (specific attitudes, perceived barriers, knowledge, and personal norms) (Petrescu-Mag, R. 2020). Many respondents stated that they find it difficult to connect their pro-environmental attitudes to their purchases, highlighting the gap that currently exists between serious environmental concerns and positive attitudes toward it and inappropriate behavior when it comes to purchases (Rincón, A.; Barbosa, R.; 2021). Their purchasing habit frequently becomes unsustainable due to a lack of time, product search, or information. Their study of Swiss consumers revealed that while time is a significant obstacle, favorable views toward the environment, local manufacturing, or fair trade are significant predictors of green purchasing. In addition to the fact that many people are concerned about the environment, ethical foods still have a relatively little market share due to people's hectic schedules. Sustainable consumption is defined as "the use of goods and services that respond to basic needs and bring a better quality of life, while minimizing the use of natural resources, toxic materials, and emissions of waste and pollutants over the life cycle, so as not to jeopardize the needs of future generations" (Prothero, A.; Dobscha, S. 2011). It is widely acknowledged that a sustainable approach to the private consumption pattern assumed by all individuals is important and desirable, but regrettably, the primary cause of environmental degradation (Juvan, E.

2014). There is now widespread agreement that consumers should be urged to switch to sustainable food consumption, which is described as "diets with low environmental impacts which contribute to food and Buyers Proteins and Nutritions security and to healthy life for present and future generations." Sustainable food consumption maximizes natural and human resources while protecting and respecting biodiversity and ecosystems, being culturally acceptable, accessible, economically fair, and reasonably priced, and providing consumers with enough nutrition, safety, and health (Young, W.; Hwang, K. 2009). In order to ensure alignment with human and environmental health, enhance democratic accountability, encourage food citizenship, and address current power imbalances, a shift toward more sustainable food consumption will necessitate fundamental changes in the organization, control, and regulation of the food system (Yamoah, F.A.; Acquaye, A. 2019).

3.STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Despite the growing interest in eco-friendly and organic food consumption, there exists a significant research gap in understanding buyers' behaviour towards the purchase of eco-friendly food products in Kolar District. Most existing studies on eco-friendly food consumption are conducted at the national or metropolitan level, with limited focus on district-specific and semi-urban–rural contexts like Kolar. As a result, local socio-cultural, economic, and agricultural factors influencing buyers' behaviour remain underexplored. There is a lack of empirical research examining awareness levels, perception of eco-friendly labels, and trust in certification systems among consumers in Kolar District. Additionally, insufficient attention has been given to price sensitivity, availability, and accessibility, which are critical factors in influencing purchase decisions in agrarian regions. Another major gap is the limited analysis of demographic and psychological factors, such as education, income, health consciousness, and environmental concern, and how these variables shape purchase intention and actual buying behaviour. Existing studies also tend to focus more on attitudes rather than the gap between intention and actual purchase behaviour. Furthermore, research has largely ignored the influence of local farmers, traditional markets, and farmer–consumer direct marketing channels in promoting eco-friendly food products in Kolar. The impact of government schemes, awareness programs, and digital platforms on consumer behaviour has also not been adequately studied. Hence, there is a clear need for a comprehensive, district-specific study to bridge these gaps and provide actionable insights for policymakers, marketers, and sustainable agriculture stakeholders in Kolar District.

4.OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1.To examine the impact of buyer's perspective and their buying behavior towards purchasing Eco-friendly food products.
- 2.To examine the impact of market conditions and buying behavior of customers towards purchasing Eco-friendly food products.

5. HYPOTHESES

- H0: There is no significant impact of buyer's perspective and their buying behavior towards purchasing Eco-friendly food products.
- H1: There is a significant impact of buyer's perspective and their buying behavior towards purchasing Eco-friendly food products.
- H0: There is no significant impact of market conditions and buying behavior of customers towards purchasing Eco-friendly food products.
- H2: There is a significant impact of market conditions and buying behavior of customers towards purchasing Eco-friendly food products.

6. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

From the consumer perspective, the study examines awareness, attitudes, preferences, and factors such as health consciousness, environmental concern, price sensitivity, and trust influencing buyers' behaviour towards eco-friendly food products in Kolar District. It also analyzes demographic influences and the gap between purchase intention and actual buying behaviour. From the market perspective, the study focuses on availability, pricing strategies, distribution channels, branding, certification, and promotional practices of eco-friendly food products. It further evaluates challenges faced by marketers and farmers in reaching consumers and identifies opportunities to strengthen the eco-friendly food market in Kolar District.

7. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The descriptive analytical research strategy serves as the foundation for the research technique. In order to comprehend the consumption of eco-friendly foods in Kolar District, the study's purpose was methodically handled and examined in depth in the analysis part. The study's goal is to evaluate the literature on introduction and develop a conceptual framework. Eco-friendly food consumption in Kolar District was examined in relation to a number of elements, including home consumer characteristics and marketing factors.

8. POPULATION, SAMPLING METHOD AND SAMPLE SIZE

For this reason, cluster sampling was used. The Kolar District was selected as the primary research area. This area was separated into four clusters: north, south, east, and west. The research sample consisted of 892 customers who regularly eat eco-friendly food items. The study includes the respondents who cooperated fully to supply all the information.

9. DATA COLLECTION

Primary Data

For the first time, data was collected using a structured, self-administered questionnaire that was created and requested to be completed. Respondents were also interviewed in-person. The "5-point Likert scale" was included in a structured questionnaire. The official language of Karnataka state, Kannada, was used for a semi-structured interview with open-ended conversation.

Secondary Data

The secondary data was gathered from the following sources: selected peer-reviewed articles from bibliographic databases (Emerald, Sage journals online, Science Direct, Scopus, Taylor & Francis online, Web of Science, and Wiley (online library)). Based on their greatest influence on the field of study and their knowledge validity, peer-reviewed journals were taken into consideration. Internet-Based Resources, Reports, journals, theses, periodicals, research pieces, newspapers, etc. that have been published.

10. DATA ANALYSIS

The primary statistical method for determining the significant association between consumer perspective and market conditions with buying behavior of consumers towards eco-friendly food consumption in Kolar District was tested by using multiple regression analysis. Reliability analysis is done to determine the research instrument's stability and consistency. Consistency demonstrates how effectively the model and conceptual framework are measured by the research tool.

11. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. All of the data in this study was self-reported and dependent on subjective views, which is a major disadvantage.
2. However, this strategy has drawbacks for consumers of eco-friendly food. The author's challenges in obtaining thorough data on agriculture and food security in cities alone are among the study's weaknesses.
3. The data utilized in this study is rather "outdated," and because of chronological differences, it might not accurately reflect the current situation.
4. The drawback of the spending survey is that if the value of food produced locally is not noted or recalled, it tends to underestimate food expenditures.
5. The study may have made use of sophisticated statistical methods. It's possible that the other relevant research variable was overlooked.
6. This study solely looked at consumer satisfaction with eco-friendly food consumption in the Kolar District. The inability to get a precisely defined measure of the elements influencing sustainable food consumption is a typical shortcoming in the literature on the subject.
7. Because some of the respondents may not be interested in providing accurate information, the information they provided may be prejudiced.

12. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table:1 Buyer’s perspective and their buying behavior towards purchasing Eco-friendly food products

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.975 ^a	.950	.943	.25853		
ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	187.451	19	9.866	147.606	.000 ^a
	Residual	287.116	879	.067		
	Total	596.373	891			
<i>b. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction</i>						
Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	-0.584	0.135		-4.344	0.000
	Food consumption frequency	0.102	0.061	0.095	1.673	0.088
	Choice of food	0.010	0.036	0.011	0.276	0.874
	Life style of the consumer	<i>0.184</i>	<i>0.059</i>	<i>0.147</i>	<i>3.128</i>	0.004
	Environmental Concern	<i>-0.142</i>	<i>0.047</i>	<i>-0.135</i>	<i>-3.018</i>	0.005
	Knowledge of eco-system	<i>0.026</i>	<i>0.036</i>	<i>0.026</i>	<i>0.729</i>	0.472
	Consumer Knowledge	<i>-0.094</i>	<i>0.041</i>	<i>-0.096</i>	<i>-2.299</i>	0.036
	Consumer Lifestyle	<i>0.050</i>	<i>0.032</i>	<i>0.049</i>	<i>1.575</i>	0.120
	Buyer Choice	0.007	0.033	0.007	0.204	0.844
	Customs traditions and values	0.000	0.037	0.000	0.000	1.000
	Buyer’s Mind set	0.017	0.057	0.015	0.299	0.788
	Focus on Agri Products	<i>0.072</i>	<i>0.027</i>	<i>0.081</i>	<i>2.644</i>	0.011
	Health Issues	<i>0.287</i>	<i>0.048</i>	<i>0.239</i>	<i>5.958</i>	0.000
	Quality of food	<i>0.185</i>	<i>0.042</i>	<i>0.214</i>	<i>4.413</i>	0.000
	Buyers Diet consciousness	<i>-0.117</i>	<i>0.050</i>	<i>-0.144</i>	<i>-2.321</i>	0.029
	Buyers Proteins and Nutrition	<i>0.056</i>	<i>0.038</i>	<i>0.069</i>	<i>1.480</i>	0.143
	Product acceptance	<i>0.246</i>	<i>0.043</i>	<i>0.346</i>	<i>5.759</i>	0.000
	Feeling self-responsibility	-0.016	0.050	-0.015	-0.322	0.742
	Social Identity	<i>0.167</i>	<i>0.053</i>	<i>0.133</i>	<i>3.172</i>	0.005
Peer Groups	<i>0.104</i>	<i>0.040</i>	<i>0.102</i>	<i>2.618</i>	0.023	
<i>a. Dependent Variable: Buying Behavior of Eco-friendly food products</i>						

A multiple regression analysis was used to investigate the effect of 19 variables of consumer factors influencing eco-friendly food consumption by consumers in Kolar District. From the above table it is understood that consumer factors (R = .975a, indicating a high degree of correlation among the variables, $t = 23.846$, $p < .01$) had a positively significant effect on sustainable food consumption by customers. Hence, it can be concluded that if the average level of customer factors were high, the average level of sustainable food consumption by consumers would also be high. The analysis also reveals that customer personal factors were able to explain the total variation in sustainable food consumption by customers. The regression model about R² 95% being high indicates the model fits the data well. Thus answering the hypothesis H1: There is a significant impact of buyers’ perspectives and their buying behavior towards purchasing eco-friendly food products. *posited for this research is accepted.* The coefficient table shows the contribution of

each consumer's personal factors. From the above table the beta values demonstrate the unique contribution for the variables such as Food consumption frequency ($\beta = 0.102, p < 0.088$), followed by Life style of the consumer ($\beta = 0.184, p < 0.004$), Environmental Concern ($\beta = -0.142, p = .005$), Consumer Knowledge ($\beta = -0.094, p = .036$), Consumer Lifestyle ($\beta = 0.050, p = .120$), Focus on Agri Products ($\beta = 0.072, p = .011$) and Health Issues ($\beta = 0.287, p = .000$), Quality of food ($\beta = 0.185, p = .000$), Buyers Diet consciousness ($\beta = -0.117, p = .029$), Buyers Proteins and Nutrition ($\beta = 0.056, p = .143$), Product acceptance ($\beta = 0.246, p = .000$), Social Identity ($\beta = 0.167, p = .005$), Peer Groups ($\beta = 0.104, p = .023$) in predicting Eco-friendly food consumption by consumers in Kolar District.

Table 2: Market conditions and buying behavior of customers towards purchasing Eco-friendly food products.

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.587 ^a	.344	.635	.80270		
ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	297.166	12	24.764	38.434	.000 ^a
	Residual	566.363	879	.644		
	Total	863.529	891			
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.373	.156		8.793	.000
	Seller's selling techniques	.153	.040	.181	3.868	.000
	Buyers perceived price	-.200	.035	-.236	-5.716	.000
	Distribution Channels of eco-friendly food products	.377	.039	.440	9.641	.000
	Ingredients of the food-products	.126	.047	.160	2.650	.008
	Advertising Message	.321	.039	.277	8.280	.000
	Policy support for the eco-friendly products	-.223	.041	-.250	-5.366	.000
	Business ethics in producing products	.005	.053	.006	.094	.925
	Company's attitude towards environment	.089	.040	.094	2.193	.029
	Labeling and packaging of the products	-.033	.055	-.039	-.606	.545
	Company's mentality to protect customer health	.007	.060	.007	.113	.910
	Corporate social responsibility	.183	.057	.211	3.192	.001
	Intensity of promoting eco-friendly products	-.141	.046	-.164	-3.095	.002

a. Dependent Variable: Buying Behavior of Eco-friendly food products

A multiple regression analysis was used to investigate the effect of 12 variables of consumer factors influencing eco-friendly food consumption by consumers in Kolar District. From the above table it is understood that consumer factors ($R = .587a$, indicating a moderate degree of correlation among the variables, $t = 8.793, p < .000$) had a positively significant effect on sustainable food consumption by customers. Hence, it can be concluded that if the average level of marketing factors were high, the average level of sustainable food consumption by consumers would also be high. The analysis also reveals that marketing factors were able to explain the total variation in sustainable food

consumption by customers. The regression model about R^2 63.5% being high indicates the model fits the data well. Thus, answering the hypothesis *H2: There is a significant relationship between marketing factors and eco-friendly food consumption by consumers in Kolar District posited for this research is accepted*. The coefficient table shows the contribution of each marketing factor. From the above table the beta values demonstrate the unique contribution for the variables such as Seller's selling techniques ($\beta = .153, p < 0.000$), followed by Buyers perceived price ($\beta = -.200, p < 0.000$), Distribution Channels of eco-friendly food products ($\beta = .377, p = .000$), Ingredients of the food-products of the food-products ($\beta = .126, p = .008$), Advertising Message ($\beta = .321, p = .000$), Policy support for the eco-friendly products ($\beta = -.223, p = .000$) and Company's attitude towards environment ($\beta = .089, p = .029$), Corporate social responsibility ($\beta = .183, p = .001$), Intensity of promoting eco-friendly products ($\beta = -.141, p = .002$), in predicting Eco-friendly food consumption by consumers in Kolar District.

13. FINDINGS

In predicting the consumption of eco-friendly foods by consumers in Kolar District, it is discovered that the following variables have a unique contribution: food consumption frequency, consumer lifestyle, environmental concern, consumer knowledge, consumer lifestyle, focus on agri-products and human health, food quality, plant-based diet, buyers' proteins and nutrition, product acceptance, social identity, and peer groups.

Additionally, it is discovered that the distinctive contribution of variables like company marketing strategies, buyers' perceived price, distribution channels of eco-friendly food products, ingredients of the food products, advertising message, policy support for the eco-friendly products and companies, environmental concern, social concern, and intensity of eco-friendly product promotion in predicting eco-friendly food consumption by consumers in Kolar District.

14. SUGGESTIONS

Motivating consumers in Kolar District to buy eco-friendly food products requires a combination of awareness, affordability, trust, and local relevance. One of the most effective strategies is educating consumers about the health benefits of eco-friendly and organic foods. Awareness programs, village-level campaigns, and demonstrations in local languages (Kannada and Telugu) can help people understand how chemical-free food improves long-term health and reduces medical expenses. Building trust is essential. Farmers' markets, organic fairs, and direct-to-consumer sales can allow buyers to interact with producers, increasing confidence in product authenticity. Clear labeling, certification logos, and transparency about farming practices can further strengthen trust. Price sensitivity is a major factor in rural and semi-urban areas of Kolar. Offering smaller package sizes, seasonal discounts, or cooperative-based pricing can make eco-friendly food more affordable. Government support, subsidies, or tie-ups with self-help groups and farmer producer organizations (FPOs) can also help reduce costs. Promoting the local origin of eco-friendly food products can strongly motivate buyers. Highlighting that these products are grown by local farmers using sustainable methods encourages community support and pride. Stories of farmers and their sustainable practices can emotionally connect consumers to the product. Availability and accessibility should be improved by selling eco-friendly food products

in local markets, ration shops, weekly shandies, and online platforms. Door-to-door delivery in urban areas like Kolar town can further boost sales. Finally, influencing social norms through schools, colleges, health professionals, and local leaders can encourage eco-friendly food consumption. When respected individuals advocate sustainable food choices, buyers are more likely to adopt them, leading to long-term behavioral change and increased demand for eco-friendly food products in Kolar District. are ready to purchase the ecofriendly products in the interest on environment and health.

15. CONCLUSIONS

Numerous research has shown that consumers have favorable views about sustainable eating practices, but that their sociodemographic traits also have an impact on their behavior. This study examines the factors that affect Kolar District consumers' use of environmentally friendly food. In addition, health concerns have a significant role in defining eating habits. Agri-food businesses can benefit from the results as well since they provide valuable insights into the behavior of contemporary customers. Consumers, companies, and legislators can use the study's conclusions to guide their activities around sustainable food consumption and behavior. Due to the current discrepancy between beliefs and actual behavior, consumers are currently vacillating between the comfort of reverting to old habits and the prudence of more resilient consumption. They will be able to operate more effectively in the market if they comprehend customer segmentation and accept the category to which they belong. However, companies would immediately profit from developing readily accessible consumption patterns and constructing effective marketing campaigns based on the present behavior shown in this study rather than on customers' transient sentiments. Finally, but just as importantly, it will be the duty of policymakers to take action through their policies and information campaigns to change consumer behavior from affective (involving consumers' feelings and emotions) to behavioral (being the trigger that will determine the reaction) to cognitive (changing consumers' knowledge about sustainable food consumption).

16. DIRECTIONS FOR THE FUTURE RESEARCH

The study of buyers' behaviour towards eco-friendly food products in Kolar District offers significant scope for future research due to changing consumer preferences, increasing environmental awareness, and evolving market structures. Future studies can expand the scope by examining longitudinal changes in consumer behaviour to understand how awareness, attitudes, and purchasing patterns evolve over time with increased exposure to sustainability campaigns and policy interventions. Further research can focus on comparative studies between rural and urban consumers within Kolar District to identify differences in awareness levels, willingness to pay, and consumption frequency of eco-friendly food products. Similarly, comparisons with neighboring districts can provide insights into regional variations in consumer behaviour. Another important area for future research is the role of socio-economic and demographic factors, such as income, education, age, occupation, and family size, in influencing purchase decisions. In-depth analysis of these variables can help

marketers and policymakers design targeted strategies. Future studies may also explore the impact of price sensitivity, availability, and trust in certification on purchase intention. Investigating consumer perceptions of organic labels, eco-certifications, and authenticity claims can reveal barriers to adoption. The influence of digital platforms, social media, and e-commerce on promoting eco-friendly food products in semi-urban and rural areas of Kolar District also presents a promising research direction. Additionally, research can examine the effectiveness of government policies, subsidies, and awareness programs in encouraging eco-friendly consumption. Finally, future research could incorporate behavioral models and psychological factors such as environmental concern, health consciousness, and social influence to develop predictive frameworks for eco-friendly food purchasing behavior, thereby contributing to both academic literature and practical decision-making.

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